

SOME ASPECTS AND LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE PREVENTION INSPECTOR'S ACTIVITIES IN WORKING WITH MINORS AND YOUTH

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Abstract: In this article, the authors have developed proposals and recommendations regarding certain aspects of the prevention inspector's work with minors and youth, as well as addressing existing problems in this field.

Keywords: prevention inspector, minors, youth, offenses.

It is evident from the mentality, customs, and values of the Uzbek people that the family has long been considered a pillar of our nation and the foundation of state policy. The great commander Amir Timur also paid attention to the upbringing of children and the matter of their family formation at the level of state policy. However, in any time and place, there are individuals who think against society and commit acts that contradict established moral norms. It is clear that such individuals were raised in a family or were responsible for family management and child upbringing. There is a proverb in Uzbek: "A bird does what it sees in its nest." This means that if an average of three or four children grow up in such families, their upbringing and family environment will be in their hands in the future. Therefore, our people have long paid serious attention to this issue, emphasizing the responsibility not only of parents but also of residents from seven neighborhoods for raising children.

Our President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, in his works "We Will Persistently Continue Our National Development by Raising It to a Higher Level," expresses the following thoughts on raising one child. "Children's upbringing is not a process that we expect when we sow wheat or sow seeds and water them, but it is necessary to pay attention to its upbringing on a regular basis."

In the process of organizing the activities of prevention inspectors to prevent violations of rights directly among young people, it is necessary to organize them taking into account all the above-mentioned characteristics. On the contrary, its consequences can lead to negative consequences. It is very important that every prevention inspector has access to all information about the number of young people in their territory, why they are inclined to commit crimes. In preventing crimes and violations committed by young people, prevention inspectors use various methods and forms. When conducting general and individual prevention, the prevention inspector shall carry out it in accordance with regulatory legal acts and on the basis of a separate plan. The use of oral, visual, and mass media in the application of general prevention methods, as well as in cooperation with educational institutions and organizations responsible for working with youth, are effective. In this regard, it is advisable to exchange views and information with these organizations, as well as take into account the requirements and needs of preventive activities. Individual preventive activities are primarily aimed at developing positive qualities in young people who have previously committed crimes, offenses, and are prone to committing crimes.

In this case, it is advisable for preventive inspectors to involve psychologists in the process. It is known that a person is formed in the family as an individual, and in the process of socialization, the family must have a positive or negative impact on the individual, forming a certain social image. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the family environment, along with its influence on the formation of personality, ensures the process of developing spiritual and moral qualities and characteristics in it. Because the family has its own system of upbringing, persuasion, and punishment, as well as the prevention of antisocial behavior. As our teacher, K.R. Abdurasulova, emphasized, the development of human feelings and thoughts, mental and spiritual qualities, as well as the causes of violations and the conditions that led to them, as a result of studying the factors that undermine the law or the enforcement of the law, the need to look for factors that hinder its observance, becomes more pronounced. Therefore, the unhealthy socio-psychological environment in the family plays an important role in the emergence of any violation. A child is raised from the womb of the mother.

The primary legal basis for youth work is the Law "On the Prevention of Neglect and Offenses Among Minors." Article 2 of the Child Law provides legislative acts on the prevention of neglect and violations of rights among minors. It is known that the system of bodies and institutions carrying out the prevention of neglect and violations of rights among minors includes:

- commissions on juvenile affairs;
- internal affairs bodies;
- bodies of education management and educational institutions;
- guardianship and trusteeship bodies;
- health management bodies and healthcare institutions;
- labor and social protection bodies.

Bodies and institutions not specified in part one of this article shall participate in the prevention of neglect and offenses among minors in the manner prescribed by law. One of these institutions, the internal affairs bodies, within their competence, shall carry out the prevention of offenses among minors and youth. Special subdivisions of the internal affairs bodies that carry out the prevention of neglect and offenses among minors consist of subdivisions for the prevention of offenses among minors and centers for the provision of social and legal assistance to minors. Other subdivisions of internal affairs bodies, within their competence, participate in the prevention of uncontrollability and violations of rights among minors and provide necessary assistance.

Divisions of internal affairs bodies responsible for the prevention of juvenile delinquency, within the limits of their authority and based on the mechanism of mutual subordination, carry out individual preventive work with inspectors of juvenile and youth delinquency prevention. They implement measures to identify missing juveniles, as well as socially vulnerable minors, and refer them in the established manner to relevant bodies or institutions that prevent neglect and delinquency among minors. These divisions also identify individuals who involve minors in committing offenses or other antisocial actions, or commit other illegal acts against minors. Additionally, they identify parents or guardians who evade or inadequately fulfill their obligations to support, raise, and educate minors, or who negatively influence minors' behavior or treat them cruelly.

They submit proposals to relevant state bodies and other organizations regarding the application of measures of influence provided for by legislation against them. They review complaints and applications related to violations of rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of minors, their parents or persons acting in place of parents, as well as other individuals. They submit proposals to relevant bodies and institutions implementing prevention of neglect and delinquency among minors regarding the application of measures of influence provided for by legislation against minors who have committed offenses or other antisocial acts. They prepare necessary documents for placing minors in social and legal assistance centers or specialized educational institutions in accordance with established procedures. They inform relevant state bodies and other organizations about instances of neglect, abandonment, delinquency, or other antisocial behavior of minors, as well as the causes and conditions enabling such behavior. They bring minors who have committed offenses or other antisocial acts, as well as neglected and abandoned minors, to internal affairs bodies in cases and according to procedures stipulated by legislation, promptly drawing up a report about this action.

They notify the parents or guardians of minors about their arrival, study the state of educational work being carried out with minors in educational, cultural-entertainment, sports and health institutions, other organizations, circles and clubs at their place of residence, study (work), submit proposals to relevant state bodies and other organizations on eliminating the causes and conditions that enable minors to commit offenses or other antisocial actions, participate in the consideration of materials on offenses or other antisocial actions of minors by relevant bodies and institutions, keep records of offenses and other antisocial actions committed by minors, as well as parents or guardians who evade or improperly fulfill their obligations to support, raise and educate minors, or who negatively influence their behavior or treat them cruelly, and also collect and summarize information necessary for compiling statistical reports, assist guardianship and trusteeship bodies in placing orphans and children deprived of parental care.

The subdivisions of the internal affairs bodies for the prevention of juvenile delinquency shall, within the framework of their activities:

carries out individual preventive work;

take measures to identify minors declared for search, as well as minors with difficult upbringing, and send them in the prescribed manner to the relevant bodies or institutions that carry out the prevention of uncontrollability and violations of rights among minors;

Parents and guardians of minors who refuse to fulfill their obligations to provide for, educate and educate minors, or who involve minors in committing offenses or other antisocial actions, or who have committed other wrongful acts against minors, as well as parents who refuse to fulfill their obligations to provide for, educate and educate minors, shall be obliged to pay the expenses of the parents and guardians of minors in the manner prescribed by law or in the manner prescribed by law, and to pay the expenses of the guardians

consider complaints and applications of minors, their parents or persons replacing them, as well as other persons related to violations of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of minors;

make proposals to the relevant bodies and institutions carrying out the prevention of uncontrollability and offenses among minors on the application of measures of influence

provided for by legislation in relation to minors who have committed violations or other antisocial actions;

prepare in the prescribed manner documents relating to the placement of minors in social and legal assistance centers or specialized educational institutions;

inform the relevant state bodies and other organizations about facts of neglect, neglect, violations of rights or other antisocial behavior of minors, as well as the causes and conditions that make them possible;

takes minors who have committed violations or other antisocial behavior, as well as minors who have been left without supervision and care, to the internal affairs bodies in the cases and in the manner prescribed by law, promptly draws a report about it and notifies their parents or guardians of parents about the arrival of minors;

studies the state of educational work carried out with minors in educational, cultural and entertainment, sports and health institutions, other organizations, clubs and clubs at the place of residence, study (work) of minors;

make proposals to the relevant state bodies and other organizations to eliminate the causes and conditions that make it possible for minors to commit violations or other antisocial actions;

participate in the consideration by the relevant bodies and institutions of materials on juvenile delinquency or other antisocial behavior;

collect and maintain records of violations and other antisocial actions committed by minors, persons who evade or do not properly fulfill their obligations to provide for, educate and educate minors, or who have a negative impact on their behavior, or who are caring for them without parental care, as well as the necessary information for the compilation of statistical reports; collect and maintain records of cases of violations committed by minors and other antisocial actions committed by minors, as well as information necessary for the compilation of statistical reports; collect and maintain records of

assist guardianship and trusteeship bodies in the placement of orphans and children deprived of parental care.

Article 5. Powers of state authorities and management bodies to ensure the rights of the child.

Within the framework of their tasks, state authorities and management bodies shall exercise the following powers: - Formation and implementation of a unified state policy to ensure the rights of the child; - Determination of priority areas for ensuring the rights of the child;

- Execution of legislation on guarantees of the rights of the child;
- Development and implementation of state and territorial programs to ensure the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of the child; - Coordination and control over the activities of state bodies, children's institutions, and organizations to ensure the rights of the child; - Financing measures to implement state policy on the protection of children's rights from the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other sources not prohibited by law, in accordance with established procedures; - Taking measures to strengthen the material and technical base of state children's institutions and to promote the development of non-state children's institutions; - Monitoring the fulfillment of international obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the rights of the child and representing the interests of the Republic

of Uzbekistan in international organizations; - Carrying out information and educational activities; - Addressing issues of support for socially vulnerable children.

The Law "On the Prevention of Offenses" provides for a normative legal document implementing work on minors in special prevention, which is one of the types of crime prevention.

The "Law on Guarantees of Children's Rights" defines the most important tasks of working with children. The following articles of the law provide for authorized bodies that ensure the rights of children.

The bodies of state power and management may exercise other powers in accordance with the legislation. In order to ensure the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of the child, to coordinate the activities of state and other bodies, organizations to protect the rights of the child, an authorized body for the rights of the child may be established in the manner prescribed by law.

In accordance with the order of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 12, 2017 No. 151 "On the procedure for organizing the activities of the subdivisions of the internal affairs bodies for the prevention of offenses," today inspectors of the internal affairs bodies are engaged in the prevention of offenses among minors and young people, as well as with minors who are in a socially dangerous situation, with minors who are inclined to commit offenses. Subdivisions for the prevention of offenses of internal affairs bodies shall organize work with minors and youth in cooperation with all sectoral services of internal affairs bodies, bodies and institutions directly responsible for the prevention of offenses, district and regional khokimiyats, non-governmental non-profit organizations and all civil society institutions and other law enforcement agencies. In particular, direct work with minors and youth is carried out by prevention inspectors of reference points, as well as inspectors of prevention of offenses among minors and youth of departments for ensuring public safety on transport. In the capital, this activity is carried out by inspectors of the prevention of offenses among minors and youth, as well as by inspectors of the support points of the internal affairs bodies, in cooperation and on the basis of legislation.

What factors should be considered in the future to raise youth consciousness?

First, to pay attention to the free thinking of young people and guide them towards scientific fields they are interested in;

Second, to effectively organize youth leisure time and assist scientifically talented young people in participating in various competitions, Olympiads, and contests;

Third, to transition to an innovative teaching system in order to develop young people's ability to analyze in new ways, enhance skills of systematic analysis and philosophical thinking, create conditions to reinforce knowledge acquired in the educational process and apply it in practice, and in this regard, prevention inspectors should provide recommendations to various higher education institutions;

Fourth, to widely involve young people in active creative activities, assist them in participating with relevant and promising innovative projects in competitions held at the national and international levels, and help this type of youth in the mahalla to advance through the Youth Union in the regions;

Fifth, it is necessary to reward and encourage talented, patriotic, capable, and gifted youth both spiritually and materially, while generalizing the experience and achievements of the National Program for Personnel Training.

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